

COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF CEMENTS FOR FIXING STRUCTURES MADE OF ZIRCONIUM DIOXIDE

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Abstract

The effectiveness of orthopedic treatment of patients using fixed prosthetic structures depends on their high-quality fixation on the supporting teeth. In order to improve the adhesion of the material to the tooth tissues, in recent years, special attention has been paid to adhesive fixation systems that improve the fixation of dentures not only to enamel, but also to dentin. Adhesion of dental materials to dentin is difficult due to its heterogeneity. With the development of adhesive dentistry, all-ceramic restorations have become more widely used. The development and introduction into practice of composite cements has led to a change in the technique of fixing ceramic restorations using adhesive systems. Thus, the problem of choosing a material for fixing all-ceramic prostheses remains relevant. Clinical practice dictates the need for a clear differentiated approach when using modern composite cements, depending on the type of restoration.

Keywords: *zirconium prostheses, adhesion of composite cements, glass ionomer and composite cements.*

In recent years, patients' demands for the aesthetics of dental structures have increased significantly, which was one of the reasons for the widespread use of metal-free prostheses based on zirconium dioxide (zirconia), which has high mechanical and optical properties and low thermal conductivity. Due to the high resistance of the material to fracture and its chemical inertness, the use of these dentures is extremely promising in dental practice. Over time, such designs, apparently, can constitute an alternative to metal-ceramic products.[1/3]

One of the most common complications, according to domestic and foreign authors, is a violation of the fixation of structures made of zirconium dioxide, therefore one of the most important in dental practice is the issue of choosing optimal fixing materials, which will help increase the effectiveness of orthopedic dental treatment.[2.4]

The purpose of the study is a primary analysis of the results of using certain cements for fixation of structures based on zirconium dioxide.

Material and methods.

An experimental study was carried out on the adhesion strength of materials based on phosphate and glass ionomer cement with zirconium dioxide samples under conditions identical to those in the oral cavity. 16 standard templates based on dioxide and 5 standard samples of fixing materials based on phosphate (visphate, viscin) and glass ionomer cements used to fix the templates were used. The samples were incubated in a humid environment simulating oral conditions for three days. The bond strength of the zirconia-based structure and fixing materials was tested in a universal testing machine. The rupture zone of a metal-free structure based on zirconium dioxide and a fixing material was tested using a light-optical microscope.

Results.

Two series of experimental studies of the adhesion strength of twenty standard templates based on zirconium dioxide were carried out using standard samples of fixing materials based on phosphate and glass ionomer cements used for fixing templates. The time for complete hardening of the cements was determined. For zinc-phosphate cement visphate it was 6.13 ± 0.35 minutes; for zinc-phosphate cement viscin it was 6.43 ± 0.41 minutes. For glass ionomer cements fuji-1 and fuji-2, the curing time was 5.83 ± 0.94 min and 6.05 ± 0.82 min, respectively, however, for the final "ripening" of the cements, the samples were kept for 24 hours before testing. The ranges of indicators in general corresponded to the literature data.

When studying the adhesion strength when using zinc phosphate cement for fixation of both samples, it was shown that minimal force is required to break the bonds between the fixing material and zirconium dioxide. To destroy the adhesive strength when using both samples of glass ionomer cements in the "fixing material—zirconium dioxide" system, the required force was less than 1.0 N/mm².

Conclusion.

An experimental study showed the insufficient strength of the fixing bonds of standard templates based on zirconium dioxide when using fixing materials based on phosphate and glass ionomer cements. Cements used without adhesive systems cause the formation of localized stress concentration points along the surface of the treatment at the moment the load is applied. The use of zinc phosphate or glass ionomer cement samples for fixation of structures based on zirconium dioxide under prolonged exposure to a humid environment leads to the formation of weak adhesion, which is insufficient for practical use. The results of the

study indicate the need to continue studying the strength of the fixing bonds of zirconium dioxide with samples of other fixing materials. It is expected that, based on the research carried out, the choice of materials for fixing metal-free structures based on zirconium dioxide will be scientifically justified.

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